

AMIR TIMUR'S GREAT SERVICES IN THE WORLD**Mashrabalieva Durдона Marufjon kizi****Student of Namangan state university****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176511>**

Annotation: This article is about the great entrepreneur, statesman, Amir Temur, his role in world politics, measures to create a single space that will serve to strengthen mutual relations between Europe and Asia.

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Since we got rid of the autocratic regime, we have been fearlessly covering our unbiased history, and ample opportunities are being created for us to gradually restore our history, which was changed and forgotten during the time of the former union, and to reveal it to the public.

There are many works and scientific articles written about Amir Temur. But it's a pity that we still don't have a comprehensive literature on them, a carefully studied critical cross-analysis of the sources, and a lack of scientific works that have been deeply scientifically analyzed or aimed at a wide readership in Central Asia, which is Temur's homeland and the territory of the state he created.

In Temur's constitutions, in terms of state and legal issues, thorough research was not carried out. The fact that Amir Temur was one of the great rulers who left a bright mark in the history of Uzbek statehood, that it was with the efforts of this person that the tyranny of the Genghises, who created political disunity in the 14th century, was ended, that he established a centralized state in a huge area stretching from the Great Wall of China to India, and to the Mediterranean Sea in the west, introduced a just order and legislation, the first constitutional document aimed at protecting human interests, "Tuzuk's" is of great importance from a scientific and theoretical point of view.[1]

But it was not possible to recognize this until recent years, because the old regime was very afraid that the emergence of a work with such great scientific potential would stimulate the awakening of the Uzbek people and recognition of their identity. In the West, monographic generalized works have appeared, starting from various information about the greatness and uniqueness of Temur's personality, which has been reflected in world history. But even in them, the issues of Amir Temur's state and rights were not sufficiently covered.

The essence of the legislation of Amir Temur's era, the citizen and the state are at the center of it. The well-known scientist Azamat Ziya highly evaluates this, saying that during the time of Amir Temur, "The interests of citizens were in the first place in legislation"[2]. This is an important lesson for all time. After all, an economically helpless state weakens and decays. Economic power is created by the people. The role of fair legislation is incomparable. One of the bright aspects of Amir Temur's genius is measured by his ability to understand this truth and demonstrate it in practice. After all, since we are building a great country in the future, there is no doubt that the spiritual principles of the past will lead us to high development through fair ways. Such a great Master looked for measures to create a single space that would serve to strengthen mutual relations between Europe and Asia. He paid great attention

to the establishment of mutual trade and economic relations. He established good relations with influential countries of the world. [3]

In the history of the world and the state and law of Uzbekistan, the era of Temur and the Temurids of the XIV-XV centuries has a special place. Amir Temur made a great contribution to the history and civilization of the world nations with the creation of this state and his statesmanship, which was recognized by the international scientific community. We can briefly include the following:

- a) he laid the foundation for the rise of the Turkish Islamic state and civilization in Central Asia (Hilda Huckham). freed the peoples of Central Asia, Khorasan, Iran, and Afghanistan from the Mongol invaders;
- b) put an end to political divisions and conflicts in this area and created a powerful centralized state;
- c) Helped Russia to get rid of the Mongol tyranny;
- d) restored and developed the international “Great Silk Road” connecting the West and the East;
- e) introduced the glory of Movarunnahr to the world, developed science, crafts, architecture, art and culture to an unprecedented level, that is, laid the foundation for the renaissance of the Temurids;
- j) raised the state system to a higher level in human development, introduced new laws and procedures.
- or) perfected military art.

Today, Uzbekistan’s constitutional way of building a democratic legal state has its historical roots in the form of the state of Temur and the Timurids. Amir Temur did not point out in “Tuzuks” that “if the state is not built on the basis of religion and law, if it is not tied to the law, then the kingdom will lose its charm, power and order”.

The emergence of the Timurid state, its centralization, economy, science development policy, Timurid renaissance is not a coincidence, but the result of the internal development of the people of Uzbekistan at that time. Over the centuries, our statehood, the noble qualities of our people, such as high spirituality, justice, and enlightenment, have developed organically with the teachings of Eastern philosophy and Islam.

It is no exaggeration to say that Amir Temur turned the capital Samarkand into the capital of the world and Bukhara into a religious center. For example, during his lifetime, the palace historians wrote a verse that says “Samarkand’s saikali royi zamin ast, Bukhara’s power is under Islam”. From the time of the Holy Prophet until now, no country has been able to produce as many imams, priests and sheikhs as Movaunnakhr produced during the time of Timur.

By giving a legal assessment to the state of Amir Temur, we should evaluate it based on the Islamic legal views of the Muslim state and its leader in determining the form of its management, the degree of absoluteness of the centralized, single governorship. The uniqueness of Amir Temur as the head of a Muslim state was that he also participated in the legislative power. By creating “Tuzuks”, he raised his country to a higher level. Based on these, it is possible to assess his state as a kind of oriental, absolute monarchy state.

References:

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